

D4.1 Reconfiguration Toolbox v1

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Flex4Res members of consortium

Table 1 Consortium members

Partner name	Shortcode	Website link
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VOESTALPINE HIGH PERFORMANCE METALS DIGITAL SOLUTIONS GMBH	VOE	https://www.voestalpine.com/group/en/
SIDENOR VIOMICHANIKI CHALYVA ANONYMI ETAIRIA	SID	https://sidenor.gr/en/
HANS BERG GMBH&CO KG	HANS	https://www.berg-kg.de/de/
GOIMEK S COOP	GOI	https://www.goimek.com/es
SORALUCE S. COOP.	SOR	https://www.soraluce.com/en
EIT MANUFACTURING CENTRAL GGMBH	EITM	https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/
NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	https://www.netcompany-intrasoft.com/
CONTACT SOFTWARE GMBH	CONT	https://contact-software.com/
A1 DIGITAL INTERNATIONAL GMBH	A1	https://www.a1.digital/
BEIA	BEIA	https://beia.be/
SAVVY DATA SYSTEMS SL	SAV	https://www.savvydatasystems.com/es/inicio
MONDRAGON CORPORACION COOPERATIVA SCOOP	MON	https://www.mondragon-corporation.com/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	TU Wien	http://www.ift.at/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	PTW	https://www.ptw.tu-darmstadt.de/
UNIVERSITAET SIEGEN	USI	https://www.uni-siegen.de/start/
IDEKO S COOP	IDE	https://www.ideko.es/

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List of Abbreviations

Table 2 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
API	Application programming interface
CBR	Case-based reasoning
ERD	Entity Relationship Diagram
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GUI	Graphical user interface
HCSRT	Human centric shopfloor reconfiguration tool
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of things
MILP	Mixed Integer Linear Programming
MIP	Mixed Integer Programming
MPS	Master scheduling problem
MTO	Make to order manufacturing
RT	Reconfiguration toolbox
SKU	Stockkeeping units
TSK	Takagi-Sugeno-Kang
WMS	Warehouse Management System

Executive summary

Deliverable 4.1 is a major step forward for the Flex4Res project as it introduces the Reconfiguration Toolbox in its initial form for the manufacturing systems; micro, macro, and meso levels. In this report the multifaceted activities undertaken during the first 18 months of the Flex4Res project, outlining the corresponding outcomes in alignment with the project's overarching objectives. Providing an exhaustive breakdown of activities and concepts across individual tasks and the description of the reconfiguration tools, this report is the first outcome of the Flex4Res developments and advancements of WP 4. Below described are the 6 tools and their corresponding hierarchical levels.

Macro Level:

Master Production Scheduler- The Master Production Scheduling is a decision-support tool for manufacturers upon master production scheduling problems, which Incorporates demand planning into the long-term manufacturing plan, manage production operations for delivering the market demand, defines cross-facility and customer delivery transportations and considers supply-chain fluctuations and plan material requirements for the production process.

Macro & Meso Level:

Macro- Meso Transition Tool - The Macro- Meso Transition Tool bridges the information gap between the macro and meso level, by projecting the overall market demand of product categories into specific product stockkeeping units (SKU) for meso level operation.

Meso Level:

Productions Scheduling Tool - The Productions Scheduling Tool provides an online (dynamic) production scheduling solution responsible for scheduling the mid/ short term production horizon, in a way that best facilitates the market demand, reduces production costs, and increases the profit of the organization.

Shopfloor Reconfiguration Tool - The Shopfloor Reconfiguration Tool for the resilient scheduling of jobs on the shopfloor and resilient reconfiguration of the remaining ones in case of a disturbance (e.g. machine breakdown). It takes the different requirements of tasks in terms of machine, clamping system and cutting tool into account.

Human Centric Shopfloor Reconfiguration Tool - The Human-centric shopfloor reconfiguration tool (HCSRT henceforth) provides managers and operators of shopfloors the ability to generate, consult and modify production schedules that factor in a multitude of technical and laborer-related constraints and eventualities with the aim of optimizing shopfloor production times and supporting resilience.

Micro Level:

Fault Detection & Human Assistance System - The Fault Detection & Human Assistance System consists of two tools being designed for early detection of faults in the machine, trigger reconfiguration needs, and assist operators in performing the reconfiguration task on resource level.

The tool employed in compiling this document is rooted in the active involvement of WP4 tasks leaders and technical providers, who not only spearheaded coordination efforts within their respective WPs but also gathered insights from task leaders, ensuring a holistic report of the Flex4Res Reconfiguration Toolbox v1 during the project's first half undertaken activities.

The overview of all the tools being developed in work package 4 are depicted in figure below:

Figure 1 Overview of reconfiguration tools being developed in work package 4

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The ability to reconfigure production systems is crucial for ensuring long-term performance and sustainability in today's volatile global economy. Various factors such as natural disasters, supply chain disruptions, and geopolitical uncertainty have highlighted the vulnerability of manufacturing facilities and resources. These disruptions not only impact operational continuity but also pose significant risks to financial performance and competitiveness. Creating reconfigurable production systems can enhance overall robustness by allowing enterprises to detect the need for reconfiguration at different levels, from supply chains to individual resources, and take appropriate actions. By leveraging these technologies, firms can thrive in an environment characterized by unpredictability and change while mitigating future uncertainties.

1.2 Work package objectives

Flex4Res aims to develop and deploy a comprehensive toolbox for implementing reconfiguration across three distinct industrial hierarchical levels: micro, meso, and macro. The focus at the micro level is on machinery and device level—local, on-site components essential to daily operations. At the workstation level, the goal of the toolbox is to determine strategies for effective adjustment of operation stages in resource level. The meso-level includes production lines and systems used by the entire organization, dealing with reconfiguration strategies for multi-stage production steps. Lastly, at the macro level, attention moves to the full value and supply chain network. This larger view considers optimization for enabling reconfiguration in complete value chains. WP4 is dedicated to comprehensively implementing

the reconfiguration tool triggered by resilience tools which includes development of AI-based algorithms facilitating reconfiguration at different levels.

1.3 Deliverable requirements

The WP4 activities and advancements are addressed in two deliverables, namely D4.1 and D4.2. These deliverables must be provided as a toolbox and a report that will describe the methodologies and implementation approaches for each tool inside the toolbox. D4.1 is the first version of this report, addressing the initial progress for the development of the Reconfiguration toolbox (v1) until M18. In the last deliverable, D4.2 which is due by M30, the complete solutions of WP4 and the implemented will be reported. The deliverables submission plan is presented in table 3.

Table 3 WP4 Deliverables

WP4 Deliverables				
Deliverable ID	Name	Leader	Due date	Status
D4.1	Reconfiguration toolbox v1	USI	M18	Submitted
D4.2	Reconfiguration toolbox v2	USI	M30	Pending

2 Reconfiguration Toolbox v1

2.1 Flex4Res approach (overview, implementation/flow diagrams)

The implementation approach in the Flex4Res project to reconfigure based on detected faults, actual disruptions, and measured levels of resilience spans different production system levels in the supply chain, namely macro, meso, and micro. In this context, the macro level refers to the broader production line and production systems, the meso level pertains to the production line and production systems, focusing on intermediate scales within these systems, and the micro level involves the machinery and device Level, addressing the smallest units within the production systems. This hierarchical approach ensures comprehensive adaptability and resilience across the entire supply chain. By making this distinction, one production system can apply reconfiguration at different setup levels, adjusting supply chain parameters accordingly. While the reconfiguration toolboxes are developed in the context of WP4, they work in synergy with the resilience assessment toolboxes corresponding to the macro, meso, and micro levels developed in Work Package 3. The reconfiguration toolboxes (RT) are described in the next sections, and the technical approach of the reconfiguration tools is depicted in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2 The technical approach of the Reconfiguration Toolboxes

2.2 Reconfiguration toolbox – macro level

2.2.1 Master Production Scheduler

2.2.1.1 Objective

Master scheduling (also referred to in the past as “macroplanning tool”) is a complex decision-making problem, dealing with planning the production, storage, and transportation of certain commodities, in a profitable and effective manner for the organization. It is part of the central management decisions of a manufacturing entity and affects its long-term performance and competitiveness in the field. From a production perspective, master scheduling deals with the integration of the market demand fluctuations in the **demand planning** decisions for the whole production network. Such an objective is crucial for manufacturers while trying to assess the market demand in a set of future periods and aim to satisfy the demand in the most cost-effective way. Manufacturers rely on such decisions to estimate the resources required to achieve these planning objectives from the production perspective. This aspect is also known as **production** and **operation planning**, which defines how production must operate to produce certain commodities in a given timeframe. An additional, and equally important set of decisions for manufacturers is associated with the **supply planning**, in other words the raw material requirements for producing the final customer product. Supply chain fluctuations in pricing and availability pose a major risk for the organization in achieving the overall planning objectives for the system. Last yet not least, **logistics** and **inventory planning** are equally important for minimizing costs associated with storing or transferring materials across different production points, suppliers, and customer channels.

The main objective of this module is to provide an integrated planning solution for the whole production network in terms of logistics, inventory, production operations and capacity, market demand and materials supply. The interdependent nature of such planning problems forces engineers to acquire a holistic planning solution which can incorporate volatile behavior in the model and result in resilient planning decisions. On the other hand, such a unified solution poses various implementation challenges, particularly in the development of a model that can be time-wise effective, trustworthy in finding (near) optimal solutions, and reconfigurable to fit a wide range of industrial cases, all of which should be adjustable by the user.

2.2.1.2 Approach

Addressing such a complex optimization problem requires structuring information in a way that can capture all the industrial requirements in terms of planning. Also developing an efficient optimization algorithm that can be tuned and adjusted to the user’s needs. This activity has utilized and will utilize knowledge extracted from the end-user to make a holistic information model of the production scenarios and problems, and in extend develop a mathematical optimization model converting hierarchically structured production data into a Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) model which can be solved by multiple optimization algorithms, such as analytical methods, heuristics, and metaheuristics. Within Figure 3 an abstract representation of the Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) used to describe the information required for the Master Scheduling Problem (MPS) is provided. Although the actual ERD of the developed software extends beyond these entities and relations, this schema represents in a holistic and clear manner the different types of objects involved within the optimization problem. The main objective of the proposed model design was to capture production information in a way that could portrait a range of different industrial scenarios and problems associated with master scheduling.

Figure 3 Abstract Overview Schema of Entity Relationship Diagram

The aforementioned information model would be generated on a new schedule optimization request to capture the industrial scenario to be optimized. The context of each individual entity of the model is described below:

MasterSchedulingScenario

Superclass containing all required information which describes the specific master scheduling problem.

<i>Facility</i>	A manufacturing entity of the production network (grid) which can produce and store a portfolio of different products requested by the market or other facilities within the organization.
<i>ProductionLine</i>	Part of a <i>Facility</i> entity which facilitates the production process of that facility with certain efficiency and specifications in product quality and production rate.
<i>OperationalMode</i>	The available modes of operation of a specific <i>ProductionLine</i> expressing the capacity of the line and productivity. This entity is a discretization of the cost-curves of the production line and express relations between fixed costs and working hours of the line.
<i>ProductOperationalMode</i>	Subclass of <i>OperationalMode</i> to express the specific cost and productivity curves to produce certain products with specific operational parameters. Lines with no ability to produce certain products would not provide such entities for the given product. While on the other hand different lines may produce the same product with different quality, cost, and productivity attributes.
<i>WarehouseItem</i>	Entity to express the inventory status of certain products within a specific <i>Facility</i> . These items are available to be either used in the production of other products, transferred to other facilities, or delivered to certain customer channels based on market demand.
<i>PortItem</i>	Expresses the productivity, capacity, and costs of a port of a <i>Facility</i> used to transfer products among different locations.
<i>SalesForecast</i>	Sales demand forecast associated with different <i>Facility</i> and <i>Product</i> in a given timeframe. Production relies on these predictions in order to calculate the optimal demand plan for the given <i>Facility</i> .
<i>Product</i>	Defines the different entities produced by the production lines, transferred from other <i>Facility</i> , or supplied by external suppliers.
<i>BillOfMaterial</i>	The bill of <i>Product</i> required to produce a given <i>Product</i> entity. Production lines use this information to define the material requirement on-input during production. These products should be available in inventory during the specific production period.
<i>BuyOption</i>	Defines the different supply chain options for purchasing products from external suppliers. Options may include multiple supplier markets for the same product with different pricing and quantity characteristics over a given period. In addition, buy options may express not only raw

material supply but also outsourcing the production of certain final/ semi-final products which is usually required during high-production demand. It needs to be noted that buy options do not express internal production network supply of product (meaning receiving products from a different *Facility* entity within the organization).

Transportation

Expresses the capacity of transporting different products between facilities or customer channels and all associated costs and *MeansOfTransportations*. This entity may express both internal and external transportation.

The aforementioned information would describe the master production scheduling problem for the manufacturing network in a discrete time horizon. Figure 4 and Figure 5 illustrate the problem in an overview, expressing it as continuous material flows, in discrete time intervals, flowing across different edges of the network. As such, the problem can be reformulated in the sense of defining the right equilibrium of material flows across the different locations to facilitate the customer demand, while maintaining a low production cost and increasing the profit. On the the facility level, the production process is formulated in a similar manner, with raw material entering the production line and converted into the output product, while also semi-products (products that may not satisfy quality standards to be considered products), scrap (and thus potentially raw material), and waste (a small percentage of the material lost in the environment during the process). Production lines may also be designed in a sequential manner, thus making a seamless material flow across the different lines while passing the product across the different production stages. As such a complex network of different materials could be created across the different lines, on which the planner should define the operational plan for the line to achieve producing the demand requested by the network, while consuming inventory raw material.

Figure 4 Overview schema of production network material flows

Figure 5 Schema of production line material flows of different materials

To solve the optimization problem the mathematical model is constructed out of the production data presented above. The mathematical model is a Mixed Integer Programming model consisted of deterministic input parameters, decision variables, constraint expressions, and objective functions. Table 4 represents the scale of the problem with respect to different set of inputs. As can be seen, the unified

mathematical model is characterized by smaller interdependent optimization problems which are lined together using mathematical expressions to ensure the generation of a feasible master production scheduling solution.

Figure 6 Set of input and output information for the Master Production Scheduling optimization service

In Figure 6, an abstract representation of the inputs and outputs of the MIP model is illustrated. The input parameters represent the data that is used to construct the model's constraints and objective function in a parametric manner, with respect to certain decision variables. The decision variables themselves are initialized based on the scale of the problem. An indication of the problem scale in terms of decision variables is displayed in Table 4. The input sets define the production scenarios and represent individual indices of the decision variables. Increasing these sets in size, would result in the increase of the decision variable matrices, and thus the overall scale of the model. As can be seen in Figure 6, some of the input parameters are fluctuating in time domain. This means that within the planning horizon of the model, these parameters may not be static, but dynamically volatile based on external factors. This is one of the key reasons why resilience is important in this management decision. Each optimization process generates the predefined set of outputs based on the optimal setup of the input costs and profits. In other words, the effectiveness of the plan is very much dependent on the realization of these parametric values in the future. In the case of the demand forecast for example, engineer constructs a statistical analysis to result in the most probable demand expectation on each planning interval. The longer the horizon, the higher the uncertainty of this value. The optimization model, however, creates a plan while taking as predetermined these aspects, unaware of statistical measurements and consequences. As such the requirement for a resilience assessment software is identified heavily here.

Table 4 Characteristics of mathematical optimization model developed for master production scheduling software

Type	Description	Index Count (Problem Scale)
Sets	Planning periods (\mathcal{T}), facilities (\mathcal{F}), production lines (\mathcal{R}^f), operational modes (\mathcal{O}^r), products & subproducts (\mathcal{P}), customer locations (\mathcal{L}), sales forecasts (\mathcal{S}), buy options (\mathcal{B}), buy options (\mathcal{B}), and means of transportations (\mathcal{M})	$(\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{R}^f, \mathcal{O}^r, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{M})$
Variables/ Expressions	Market demand	$O(\mathcal{F} \cdot \mathcal{P} \cdot \mathcal{L} \cdot \mathcal{T})$
Variables/ Expressions	Production	$O(\mathcal{F} \cdot \mathcal{R}^f \cdot \mathcal{O}^r \cdot \mathcal{P} ^2 \cdot \mathcal{T})$
Variables/ Expressions	Internal transportation	$O(\mathcal{F} ^2 \cdot \mathcal{P} \cdot \mathcal{T} \cdot \mathcal{M})$
Variables/ Expressions	External transportation	$O(\mathcal{F} \cdot \mathcal{P} \cdot \mathcal{L} \cdot \mathcal{T} \cdot \mathcal{M})$
Variables/ Expressions	Supply chain	$O(\mathcal{F} \cdot \mathcal{P} \cdot \mathcal{B} \cdot \mathcal{T})$
Variables/ Expressions	Inventory	$O(\mathcal{F} \cdot \mathcal{P} \cdot \mathcal{T})$

The proposed mathematical optimization model captured all aspects defined within the problem statement, providing however some level of complexity during optimization. The model was in the class of Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) while all mathematical expressions were designed as linear transformations of the decision variables. This provided several benefits from the optimization point of view, since linear models are easily to optimize (in terms of algorithm) and usually require a shorter number of iterations for generating a near optimum solution with comparison to quadratic, convex, or non-linear models. Depending on the scale of the different sets provided on input, the model would increase or decrease in scale respectively.

Figure 7 Master Production Scheduling Software Architecture

The overall architecture of the solution is presented in Figure 7, with the blue highlighted parts being the components developed within the scope of this project. The data structure for storing production information, presented in Figure 7 will be facilitated by the Data Repository component. All necessary information for creating a new master production plan will be available within these information schemas. The business logic for structuring and handling information is hosted within the MPS main server, which is the middleware for interacting with the backend services of the software. The front-end component, i.e. MPS Web Application, is the digital thread that will allow the user to manage the operations of the software and configure its functionalities. The configuration of the software input parameters, namely, facilities, production lines, inventory, logistics, customer demand, supply network, products and bill of materials, are provided to the software in a manual or an automated way. The software will allow the user import to certain information using excel format, while connection and mapping interfaces will be developed to convert information from existing production ERP, MRP or WMS software onto the software's repository system. Depending on the user's preferences both ways will be available.

The software encompasses the optimization services within the main server, allowing the web application to execute different optimization requests. On the background, the data management module, hand-over the associated information to the optimization APIs which are sent to the optimization component. As described before, prior to optimization the mathematical model is constructed, using which is then translated to an optimizer's model using a generic connection interface. This allows the software to alter across different optimizers dynamically, as long as the connecting interface is compatible with the optimizer's internal model. The outputs from the optimization process are returned to the data management services, stored within the data repository, and finally presented to the user.

2.2.1.3 Implementation

2.2.1.3.1 Overview

The implementation process focused on developing the required software components designed in the previous section and establishing all required connections in-between. The development of the data repository was facilitated using MySQL schemas. Initially the Entities Relationship Diagram (ERD) was developed in order to outline the database schema similar to Figure 3. The model was forward engineered into SQL code and the software's schema was created. The main server was initialized by creating the Data Access Objects for interacting with the data repository and construct the required queries for receiving and updating information. The specific component was developed using Spring MVC in Java and contained the business logic for structuring information provided by external software. In parallel, the optimization services were developed in Java, as a Spring service that could receive all input requirements for the model and construct the Mixed Integer Programming model using a generic connection interface developed within the scope of the project. The mathematical modelling component was responsible for mapping input data into a specific set of objects i.e. constraints, objective function, and variables, which were then converted into the corresponding objects of an optimizer. This required an extra step for converting these objects into the specific object format of different optimizers, yet it provided the capability of switching between different implementations at-will. There were developed two different connections with ORTOOLS and Gurobi optimizers to test this aspect. The output was modeled back into the software's model and sent back to the main server. The optimization services were exposed using REST APIs and connected to the APIs provided by the MPS software.

The user (production manager) was the one signifying these operations, provided production information and scenarios, and validated the result of the software. As such, there was a requirement for a UI application that would allow the user to go through all these steps easily. There were thus developed several UX designs (mock-ups) in collaboration with the industrial end-user and the initial developments using a JavaScript framework were initialized. Some initial results of the non-fully integrated front-end component of the software are presented below.

Figure 8 Login page

Figure 9 Products & Bill of Material configuration

Figure 10 Production and sales network configuration

Figure 11 Forecast scenarios configuration of stochastic parameters

Within, Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11 the initial part of the software configuration is presented. The user is able to define different production scenarios, while also initializing volatile parameters within the software. In terms of optimization, this refers to defining all the required inputs for generating a new scheduling solution. Different inputs variations as possible through the generation of different scenarios, as such allowing the user to test different “what-if” scenarios, while also allow the resilience assessment software to evaluate different scenarios and finally estimate the resilience of a given plan. The visualization of the output results and management of different solutions is on-going development activity of this solution in terms of the Web UI application.

2.2.1.3.2 Technical integration (use case)

The proposed master production scheduling software was integrated within the production digital thread by receiving information related to market demand, supply chain, and production costs via the existing industrial Enterprise Resources Planning (ERP) software. The integration was facilitated for SAP Integrated Business Planning (IBP) software product containing the current production scenarios of the industrial use-case. SAP IBP is a well-known and used planning solution, integrating handling multiple aspects of the manufacturing process, such as supply chain volatilities and forecasts, market demand and pricing results, while also extensive production cost analysis required for configuring the information model of this research result. As such, a custom connector was created to facilitate the data export process from the SAB IBP repository and save it to the local master production scheduling storage repository. Manual imports were also enabled in excel format, allowing the users to extract manual information from the ERP, process them and import them into the proposed software.

The first part required the user to configure is the main parameters of the network/ organization, such as the supply chain network, products portfolio, and bill of materials, means of transportation and customer channels. This was a process which was required once during the initialization of the software and updated at a very low frequency depending on the network's strategic decisions e.g. changing suppliers, adding or removing products.

2.2.1.3.3 Validation (use case)

The initial validation results were performed on market and supply chain scenarios from 2019 in SID organization. The dataset from that year was stored upon the master scheduling software and multiple different scenarios were tested. From the validation scenarios that have been defined in D1.1, in the subsection 2.2.3.3, the validation scenario 1 describes the objective of validating the macroplanning optimization tool, where the expected outcome is to improve the supply chain plan of Sidenor. This is an ongoing task, since the model has not been finished due to fine tuning activities.

2.3 Macro-Meso transition tool

2.3.1.1 Objective

In order to streamline the computation of the supply chain plan, some companies choose to group stock-keeping units (SKUs) together. This simplification reduces complexity and computational time compared to computing the plan with individual SKUs. Instead, the plan is computed for aggregated "product types." Once the supply chain plan is computed for a group of plants at the macro level, it needs to be disaggregated to provide actionable information for individual factories at the meso level. This involves breaking down the aggregated product types into their respective SKUs. This tool has been designed to meet the requirements of the Sidenor group. Additionally, disaggregating a product type into SKUs involves assigning quantities to SKUs belonging to a product type, such that the sum of quantities adding up to the demanded quantity of the product type.

2.3.1.2 Approach

Figure 12 Macro-Meso transition tool

The approach that is followed is described in Figure 12. To get all the information that is needed in order to disaggregate the information from product types of quantities to SKUs quantities, the supply chain plan is needed as the input. The list with the assigned SKUs to quantities for a plant of the network, is given as an input to the Production scheduling tool, to compute the scheduler of the plant/ factory.

2.3.1.3 Implementation

The Macro-Meso transition tool is implemented with JAVA programming language, and it gets information (as demand plan, inventory information, operation plan and sales) from the Master Production scheduler (see section 2.2.1) and provides the resulted SKUs to the Production scheduling tool (described in section 2.4.1) as input.

In order to do the transition from the Macro to Meso, the tool should predict the demand quantity that should be produced. In other words, in a company there are the orders that have been already made by the customers, but a company should also produce stock in case a customer makes a new order. For the sake of simplicity, the made orders are referred to as orders and the predicted demand quantity that should be produced by the company is referred to as forecasting quantity. In the current implementation the forecasting quantities are computed based on the sales of the last months. This is also considered as a limitation, and in the next months the goal is to build a forecasting tool that will results these forecasting quantities.

2.3.1.3.1 Overview

The Macro-meso transition tool aims to fill in the gap of going from SKU groups to SKUs. The required input data comes from the Master Production Scheduling tools, and in detail is information about the inventory the sales, the production plan and the demand plan. This data can be fed either from a tools like Integration Business Planning (IBP) software, or a Sales and Operation Planning (S&OP) software, directly from an ERP, or other data sources of a company.

2.3.1.3.2 Technical integration (use case)

Figure 13: Integration to Sidenor use case

In order to integrate the Macro-Meso translation tool into the Sidenor use case, two tools were used. Firstly, the *Master productions scheduler* (as described) computes the supply chain plan, and it is given as input to the *Macro-Meso transition tool*, to disaggregate the information into SKUs. After finding the SKUs for a fixed plant, then the *Production scheduling tool* it gets the list of SKUs and quantities as an input to compute the production schedule.

2.3.1.3.3 Validation (use case)

The validation phase involves the following steps:

- Step 1:** Compute supply chain plan.
- Step 2:** Disaggregate information from macro to meso level information (Product types of quantities to SKUs quantities).
- Step 3:** Compute schedule with the proposed SKUs quantities for the Thessaloniki's plant.
- Step 4:** Evaluate the proposed list of SKUs mapped with quantities from the industrial experts.
- Step 5:** Get feedback and go to Step 1.

2.4 Reconfiguration toolbox – meso level

2.4.1 Productions scheduling tool

2.4.1.1 Objective

Production scheduling is the immediate successor of master production scheduling, responsible for scheduling the mid/ short term production horizon, in a way that best facilitates the market demand, reduces production costs, and increases the profit of the organization. In contrast to master production scheduling, this software needs to provide dynamic optimization characteristics and allow adaptive interference during production operation. The shorter planning horizon, differentiated between 2-6 weeks raises several uncertainties in the production process, thus forcing production managers to adjust their production operations on the run. The main objective of this software solution is to support managers of individual production sites to handle their production and meet the mid-term production objectives in the most effective manner. The software solution was designed in a highly adaptable and reconfigurable manner, allowing a variety of industrial scenarios to be captured.

2.4.1.2 Approach

The proposed software solution builds down to the microplanning software (a.k.a. Master Production Scheduling) to receive the long-term production and operation plans, while also the expected arrival of certain material from suppliers or from other facilities. The integration mechanism between that two

software is facilitated by the meso-to-macro interfaces presented in previous section and bridge the gap between the information needed in the two software.

Figure 14 Abstract representation of ERD of the Production Scheduling software

Figure 14 displays in an abstract manner the relations between the entities provided by the production scheduling software. As can be easily identified, these entities are associated with low level scheduling information, required to define the routings for producing certain products, which are then used to extract the specific bill of processes for a certain production order. The logic of this model is that a certain product can be produced by the consumption of a list of material in the context of a process which can be facilitated by one or more resources. The bill of material required as input to the process may be available in stock, or similarly provide its own list of materials and processes capable of producing this product. In such a hierarchical logic, the production of the final product can be converted into a specific process plan required by the optimizer by backtracking all the material requirements and associated processes and decide whether to produce it or receive it from stock (if possible).

The overall software architecture is presented in Figure 15, which similarly to the MPS solution provides a business logic (main server) component, the user layer (Web UI application) and the optimization services, tailored for the specific scheduling problem. Information regarding the production orders, are received by the macro-to-meso interfaces and the required process plans are constructed accordingly. In contrast to MPS, this software uses online information from the factory to monitor the performance of the schedule and dynamically propose corrective decisions to the user. The user can configure the environment and decide the list of orders to schedule for the upcoming mid-term horizon. The scheduling API is responsible for establishing a stable connection between the software and the optimization algorithms, to send and receive the problem/ solution.

Figure 15 Production Scheduling (PS) software architecture

In order to optimize the scheduling problem, LMS implemented an algorithm, drawing from scientific research [1]], which utilizes traveler salesman problem (TSP) algorithms to formulate schedules. The relationship between scheduling and TSP is elaborated in ², with a focus on the depth of search concept, determining the number of layers examined by the search method. Key control parameters include the Decision Horizon (DH), Sampling Rate (SR), and Maximum Number of Alternatives (MNA). At each decision point governed by DH, SR, and MNA, a decision tree is generated. Illustrated below are nodes $A_1 \dots A_N$, representing decision points for task allocation to operators. The algorithm's pseudocode is detailed in Michalos, Makris & Mourtzis [2].

- Step 1:** Create alternatives by randomly creating assignments of all layers in DH, until MNA is reached.
- Step 2:** For each alternative of the Step 1, create SR random alternatives (samples) until all nodes in the alternative are searched.
- Step 3:** Calculate criteria scores for all the samples belonging to the same alternative of Step 1.
- Step 4:** Calculate the alternative's score as the average of scores achieved by this samples.
- Step 5:** Calculate the utility values of each alternative.
- Step 6:** Select the alternative with the highest utility value.
- Step 7:** Store the assignments of the selected alternatives.
- Step 8:** Repeat **Steps 1 – 8** until an assignment has been done for all the nodes of the selected branch.

Therefore, the algorithm generates a roster of permissible task-resource assignments for each decision tree. MNA governs the breadth, while DH regulates the depth of the search. SR, conversely, steers the search toward alternatives capable of yielding superior solutions. Thus, the solution's quality hinges on the choice of MNA, DH, and SR.

Figure 16 Solution generation algorithm

Figure 17 Modelling within the scheduling solution

The depicted model illustrates the structure employed by the hierarchical scheduler. The workload comprises a compilation of jobs for which the agent will devise a schedule. Within each factory, a roster of work centers exists, with each work center containing a series of resources. As the workload may vary, differing jobs with distinct tasks must be allocated to appropriate resources.

2.4.1.3 Implementation

2.4.1.3.1 Overview

The implementation of the proposed software is split into several parts. At first the database schema(s) was designed and developed in MySQL. The main server of the software was implemented in Spring-Boot framework and connected to the SQL database using JPA framework in order to allow easy transition between different SQL providers. This component provides all required interfaces for exchanging information with the data repository while also executing certain operations like scheduling. Within the following swagger description, it is shown the current version of the software APIs provided by the PS server.

OpenAPI definition v0 OAS 3.0
/3/api-docs

Servers
http://localhost:8080 - Generated server url

- Bill Of Material** Operations related to the Bill Of Material
- Processes** Operations related to processes
- Setup Matrix** Operations related to Setup Matrices
- Resources** Operations related to resources
- Products** Operations related to products
- Inventory** Operations related to inventory records
- SKU (Product Type, SKU Group, Quality Type)** Update Quality Type, Product Type, or SKU Group categories available on server
- Shift Definition** Operations related to Shifts
- Buffers** Operations related to buffer entities

Figure 18 Configuration interfaces of the scheduling data provided by the production scheduling server

Figure 19 Screenshot from overview tab

Figure 20 Screenshot from inventory stock review tab

Figure 21 Screenshot for maintenance planning tab

Figure 22 Screenshot from product definition tab

These interfaces are mainly associated with aspects of configuration and construct the part of the software which allows the user to define the production environment and setup the process plans for generating different products. The Web application was developed using Angular framework and implements these interfaces in a user-friendly manner.

2.4.1.3.2 Technical integration (use case)

The technical integration started with defining the production data for configuring the software in an initial phase. Offline information was provided in Excel formats and parsers were created on the software to be able to import new production information. Integration with the WMS and ERP were also initialized by setting up all the required security standards to access online production information associated with the inventory status. This revealed whether the production plan was going as predicted or rescheduling operation is required. Finally, integration with the macro-to-meso planning interfaces started in order to dynamically load production orders generated by the MPS solution.

2.4.1.3.3 Validation (use case)

The validation scenarios have been defined in D1.1, under subsection 2.2.3.3, and the validation scenario for the Production scheduling optimization tool is the Validation scenario 3. The expected, the expected outcome it that the schedule that the Production scheduling optimization tool results, overcome several of the gaps and problems that have identified in the Sidenor use case. Currently, the validation of the tool has not started yet.

2.4.2 Shopfloor reconfiguration tool

2.4.2.1 Objective

The objective is to develop a tool for the resilient scheduling of jobs on the shopfloor and resilient reconfiguration of the remaining ones in case of a disturbance (e.g. machine breakdown). Each task has certain requirements in terms of machine, clamping system and cutting tool (see comment below). Each task can be possible on several machines (flexible job shop problem), which are represented using the Asset Administration Shell. The inventory is not considered, and it is assumed that the supplies are always available. It is a make to order manufacturing (MTO) environment which produces individual orders and not a certain product portfolio to stock. The planning horizon is flexible and depends on the number of orders fed into the tool, it is designed for medium to short term. The tool considers set-up times and load, and unload times of the clamping system.

2.4.2.2 Approach

The chosen approach to solve the flexible job shop problem is constraint programming to find a feasible and resilient solution which considers the constraints and variables. Firstly, an initial resilient schedule is calculated and operated. As soon as there is a disturbance like a machine failure, a rescheduling is triggered, the affected machine is blocked with a repair period and a new resilient schedule (considering the repair period) with the remaining jobs is calculated. To get the resilient schedule, the algorithm first finds several feasible solutions optimized for make span, from which the best solutions are then evaluated for resilience in the resilience assessment tool and the most resilient schedule is chosen for operation.

2.4.2.3 Implementation

So far, the tool is only implemented in a test/simulation environment separate from the VOE use case.

2.4.2.3.1 Overview

The shopfloor reconfiguration tool requires several static properties from each machine-AAS, a set of orders in a file or access to a running ERP service, a disturbance to trigger the reconfiguration and a resilience assessment tool. The output of the tool is a list of all the tasks scheduled to specific machines, with a clamping system and cutting tools (see comment below). The overview can be seen in Figure 23. The orders consist of products which have workplans with steps. See Figure 24. The steps can only be manufactured on specific machines (from which there are several available), with certain clamping systems and tools (see comment below). To access the AAS properties the tool connects to the AAS

registry asking for the URLs to connect to the required machines, which it uses then to access the properties of each machine-AAS in their respective server. The AAS registry server, listing the URLs of the individual AASs, is running in a docker container, as well as the individual machine-AAS servers representing the machines.

Figure 23 Overview of the shopfloor reconfiguration tool

Figure 24 Data model of the shopfloor reconfiguration tool

2.4.2.3.2 Comment

It was originally planned to also schedule the cutting tools, according to the tool requirement and the remaining lifetime. But since the scheduling with tool change takes way too much computation time, due to the exponentially larger solution space, this feature was abandoned for now with the constraint programming method. It can be viewed as that the necessary tools are always available, with infinite lifetime and are automatically equipped with during the setup time. It is planned to solve this problem in future deliverables. For example, with reinforcement learning.

2.4.2.3.3 Technical integration (use case)

The tool is not yet integrated in the use case, only in a test/simulation environment.

2.4.2.3.4 Validation (use case)

The tool is not yet integrated in the use case, only in a test/simulation environment.

2.4.3 Human-centric Shopfloor reconfiguration tool

2.4.3.1 Objective

The objective of the Human-centric shopfloor reconfiguration tool (HCSRT henceforth) is to provide managers and operators of shopfloors with the ability to generate, consult and modify production schedules that factor in a multitude of technical and laborer-related constraints and eventualities with the aim of optimizing shopfloor production times and bolster resilience.

2.4.3.2 Approach

The approach the HCSRT follows consists of a shopfloor manager scheduling one or many work orders into a timeline representing the productive resources existing on the shopfloor (i.e., machines and operators)- the HCSRT automatically assigns the necessary sequences of operations to compatible resources based on previously defined criteria and artifacts (such as operator capacities and availability, machines status and performance, work & shift calendars, etc.), attempting to optimize resulting schedules based on pre-set criteria (target functions). The generated production schedule is propagated to the shopfloor by means of Edge devices connected to the HCSRT, and reflected through HMIs and displays, so that operators are able to consult their corresponding activities at any time and update their progress. Deviations from the generated schedule (i.e., delays or early completions) are propagated back to the HCSRT, alongside machine process data and insights from Edge-level PDM tools (such as Ideko's Cycle Analysis Tool), granting managers the ability to react to disruptions by generating alternative schedules manually, or delegating generation of schedules to 3rd party services. Integration with external services is performed by means of AAS sub models accessed over a data space, that reflect the status of production assets and the overall resilience of the shopfloor production schedule and enable adjusting setpoint parameters (target function weights) pertaining to HCSRT schedule optimization.

Figure 25 Functional architecture of the Human-centric Shopfloor reconfiguration tool

2.4.3.3 Implementation

The HCSRT has been implemented as a new functionality of Savvy's IoT platform:

- Web UI hosted on Savvy Industrial Cloud (Apache + PHP)
- Optimization module hosted on Savvy cloud infrastructure (Python)
- ML algorithm & models feeding the optimization module (Python)
- Edge-level application hosted on Savvy IoT gateway devices (Apache + PHP + Python)

2.4.3.4 Overview

In order to use the HCSRT, certain information and working artifacts need to be registered on its data model, per shopfloor:

- At least one shopfloor calendar
 - At least one shift per calendar
- At least one machine or production asset
 - At least one operator, capable of operating the machine / asset
 - Individual calendars can be defined per operator, overriding shopfloor calendar
 - Individual calendars can be defined per machine, overriding shopfloor calendar
- At least one production process (sequence of operations)
 - At least one operation that registered machines & operators are able to perform

Once the necessary information and artifacts have been registered, a user (typically a manager role) can then create & update production schedules, either manually or unattended.

1. Select "pending" Work Orders that have not yet been scheduled
2. HCSRT triggers Genetic Algorithm to generate schedules based on pre-defined target functions and weights – as the GA runs, increasingly optimized schedules are generated. The user may choose to halt GA execution at any time, with the latest generated schedule being presented
3. User may choose to manually modify the proposed schedule before submitting it to HCSRT and downstream Edge devices

In order to reflect a generated production schedule on the shopfloor and update on its progress, at least one Savvy Edge IoT gateway device needs to be deployed on the shopfloor, with a locally accessible UI-based application linked to HCSRT (henceforth referred to as "Job Manager"), which displays the current schedule, and enables operators to record the dates & times when they begin to perform different operations, report when an operation has been completed successfully, or an operation has been halted due to an incident.

1. Operator accesses the Job Manager UI and "logs in", starting their shift and accessing the schedule generated on HCSRT
2. After logging in, but prior to operating a machine, operator selects the corresponding operation on the schedule, starting the operation.
 - a. If the operation completes successfully, the operators mark it as completed on Job Manager.
 - b. If the operation is halted due to an incident or anomaly, the operator reports the issue on Job Manager – the operation can be resumed once the underlying issue is resolved or aborted.

3. Schedule progress is updated upstream on HCSRT according to reported operation completion times and incidents, and deviations from the submitted schedule are displayed in an overlay.

Progress of generated schedules is updated automatically by means of the Savvy IoT gateway continuously uploading machine process data and operation events reported by shopfloor personnel. Depending on the configuration of the shopfloor schedule, reconfiguration (rescheduling) can be triggered manually or automatically based on pre-set thresholds.

2.4.3.5 Technical integration (use case)

HCSRT has been partially integrated on the Goimek use case to test and debug its functionalities during development. It will be fully integrated for validation during 2024.

2.4.3.6 Validation (use case)

HCSRT will be validated on Goimek's Itziar shopfloor after full technical integration.

2.5 Reconfiguration toolbox – micro level

2.5.1 Fault detection and human assistance system

2.5.1.1 Objective

The Fault detection and human assistance system's objective is to provide workers and operators at the workstation level with the ability to detect and identify fault situations and help remove errors through the reconfiguration measures.

2.5.1.2 Approach

Fault detection and reconfiguration toolbox is triggered by resilience assessment toolbox, when there is a need for reconfiguration at resource level. This reconfiguration toolbox comprises of two main components.

1. Fault detection system
2. Human assistance system

The links between the Resilience and Reconfiguration Toolbox are shown in the figure below.

Figure 26 Synergy between the resilience assessment and reconfiguration toolboxes

2.5.1.3 Implementation

Fault detection system:

For the detection of fault situations and the handover of reconfiguration tasks, an approach was selected that also copes with limited data availability and utilizes the expertise of experienced operators. Fuzzy case-based reasoning (fuzzy CBR) was introduced for this purpose, which learns from the experience of experts. By using fuzzy logic, the system differs from traditional CBR systems. As a result, the variables used in the cases become fuzzy variables and there is no sharp decision variable (0 or 1) when distinguishing whether a case applies or not. Instead, it is a degree of agreement or probabilities for the occurrence of individual cases.

Case-based reasoning systems are a widespread machine learning method that takes the experience and results from an existing knowledge database and derives a proposed solution for a new problem or, for example, points out potential problems. The working process for a typical CBR is shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27 Schematic representation of how a case-based reasoning system functions

The theory of fuzzy logic works with the modelling of fuzziness of linguistic terms. In forming processes, fuzzy logic processes fuzzy variables, which come from the sharp measurement data, to control the system (according to ENGEL 1995) [3]. The fuzziness occurs in fuzzy systems when assigning the input variables to the fuzzy quantities.

In FLEX4RES, we integrate fuzzy logic to show that continuously refining the precision with which we describe the world is not invariably advantageous. Systems such as case-based reasoning or other machine learning models have the capacity to absorb information and forecast outcomes from data without direct programming intervention. "Data" in this context refers to exact, well-defined data, the utilization of which for learning and detecting problems can occasionally result in unsatisfactory outcomes. To enhance their efficiency, we introduce the concept of fuzzy logic theory, emphasizing the importance of the membership function.

In traditional crisp set theory, whether a value belongs to a set is determined in binary terms: it either belongs or does not. Fuzzy set theory introduces the notion that a value can both partially belong to and partially not belong to a set at the same time. This is realized by defining a membership function $\mu(x)$ that specifies each element x extent of belonging to the fuzzy-membership [4].

Membership functions, which describe both crisp and fuzzy sets, can vary in form. However, some types are commonly used in practical scenarios. Users can choose a membership function based on their experience, or it may be determined through machine learning techniques. These functions are graphically represented with curves, where the x-axis denotes values from the data set and the y-axis indicates the level of membership. A crisp set's membership function typically appears as a binary signal with y-axis values of either 0 or 1, whereas a fuzzy set's function might be shaped like a triangle, a trapezoid, or similar forms like Gaussian distribution (see Figure 28).

Figure 28 Triangular function (left), trapezoidal function (centre) and bell curve (right), which can be used as fuzzy sets according to KRUSE et al. (2015) [4]

The types of fuzzy controllers include the Takagi-Sugeno-Kang controller (TSK controller) and the logic-based controller. According to KRUSE et al. (2015) [4], the most used fuzzy controller is the Mamdani controller, also known as the max-min controller. The max-min controller consists of the following Elements:

1. definition of membership functions of the input variables
2. fuzzification
3. setting up the rule base
4. inference
5. defuzzification

In contrast to fuzzy controllers, it is not necessary for the fuzzy CBR to generate a sharp output value with defuzzification. Instead, this step of a typical max-min controller is deliberately omitted in order to remain fuzzy. Only the MIN operator is used to determine the degree of fulfillment H of a rule (see equation 1), where x is the input variable, A the linguistic terms of the input variables x input variable and j the number of the rule.

$$H_j = \text{MIN} \left(\mu_{A_{ij}}(x_{ij}) \right) \text{ with } i = 1, \dots, n \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

In Flex4Res, the sensor data of the smart tool, the machine data and the feedback from the resilience toolbox are used as input variables. A case is created from a rule, a membership function as output and the defined list of tasks for the reconfiguration is linked to this (see Figure 29).

Figure 29 Approach to building the case-base through the rule, the membership functions, the output and the reconfiguration option

As an example, the Figure 30 shows a rule for a case that considers the ejection of the workpieces during operation. The force of the blank holder and the maximum backward stroke force are used as input and the output is the probability of the workpiece ejection. The membership functions for the linguistic terms of the inputs and for the output are shown. With the selected size of the input data, a degree of fulfilment or probability of 60% is achieved.

Figure 30 Example of a rule and the use of the MIN operator

In practice, the operator will receive the cases with the highest degree of fulfilment as a decision-making aid. A task list for reconfiguration is linked to each case. If none of the cases in the case-base achieve a satisfactory degree of fulfilment, then the state of the machine is not normal, and the experienced operator is given the opportunity to create a new case in order to be prepared for this case in the future.

Human assistance system:

Figure 31 Flow-diagram for human assistance system

For developing a human assistance system, following are the working steps:

- Reconfiguration strategies are determined, that are relevant to the system.
- Data acquisition system consists of eye-gaze sensor, IMU sensors and video camera.
- With eye-gaze sensors intention or focus of worker is determined.
- With IMU sensors, actions of human are recorded.
- Video camera helps to record environment and disturbances.
- Sensor and data fusion is done by synchronization of time, resampling the eye tracker frame rate to 60 Hz and filtering the noises.
- Later, from the acquired data, human actions and sequence is identified for a particular reconfiguration task. This sequence is compared with the set of actions determined for the reconfiguration strategies.
- This data is then annotated and stored as a knowledge database.
- From the knowledge database, this data will be used in order to generate action sequence to perform reconfiguration task in gaming environment so as to assist the worker.
- The user interface has to be developed with Unity3D.

The experimental setup to record human actions is shown in the figure below:

Figure 32 Sketch of the structure of the system for recording motions of the operator on the press

2.5.1.3.1 Overview

The fault detection system determines the need of reconfiguration and point out the strategy. Later with simulation of particular actions and sequence in scene graph, the human is assisted to perform the task of reconfiguration and point out the strategy. Later with simulation in scene graph, the human is assisted. For the decision to reconfigure, the fault detection system takes the resilience of the machine as input and thus influences the decision through the resilience (Figure 26).

Furthermore, anomalies are recognized and used as input for quantifying resilience. In the case of unknown faults, where the fault detection system recognizes that the process is not running normally but does not determine a high probability of occurrence for one of the trained cases, the operator is given the opportunity to rectify the fault with his experience without assistance and to enter his decisions for reconfiguration into the system.

2.5.1.3.2 Technical integration (use case)

Fault detection and human assistance system is planned to be integrated in lab setup at the university of Siegen. Currently there are two setups in place. One at USI-FAMS for the human assistance system and the other one at USI-UTS for the fault detection system. The setup at the forming lab of USI-UTS will be used for both systems. The current setup includes the deep drawing tool, the zwick roell Z250 universal testing machine, the Gantner Controller Q.Station X and the hydraulics to actuate the blankholder of the deep drawing tool. But not yet integrated in the use case.

2.5.1.3.3 Validation (use case)

Fault detection and human assistance system is planned to be validated in Hans Berg.

3 Next steps

3.1 Reconfiguration toolbox – macro level

3.1.1 Master production scheduler

The next steps for this task regarding the optimization tool developed in T4.2 are to continue the fine-tuning in parallel with Sidenor and then evaluate the performance of the tool, which constitutes validation scenario 1 of D1.1. Additionally, developing the GUI is an important next step, since the primary focus was on the modelling and development of the optimization tool.

3.2 Macro-Meso transition tool

Since this task has not been defined in the GA, there is no specified validation scenario. However, section 2.3.1.3.3 outlines the next validation methodology. Specifically, the next steps for this tool are to continue its development and to conduct research on the challenge of forecasting quantities that should be produced.

3.3 Reconfiguration toolbox – meso level

3.3.1 Productions scheduling tool

Next steps for the tool are to continue the development of the GUI, to finish developments of the optimization tool, and validate the production scheduling tool based on the validation scenario 3 from D1.1.

3.3.2 Shopfloor reconfiguration tool

Next steps for the Shopfloor reconfiguration tool comprise:

- Include worker (as AAS) into scheduling
- Dynamic live scheduling of workers to machine with orders based on the current state of the shopfloor
- Include performance state of machine for scheduling (saw band lifetime)
- Include setting up tasks of machines for worker

3.3.3 Human-centric Shopfloor reconfiguration tool

Next steps for the Human-centric Shopfloor reconfiguration tool comprise:

- Deploying an AAS Server on Savvy cloud infrastructure
- Definition of an AAS sub model that reflects active shopfloor production schedules, if no suitable official IDTA sub model is available in the short term.
- Definition of an AAS sub model that reflects resilience of active shopfloor production schedules.

- Building an interoperability layer into the tool to interface with Savvy IoT platform for data provisioning, adjustment of Genetic algorithm objective function weights, and unattended rescheduling.
- Optimization and fine-tuning of Genetic Algorithm of HCSRT.

3.4 Reconfiguration toolbox – micro level

3.4.1 Fault detection and human assistance system

The next steps for the Fault detection and human assistance system are the motion capture recordings on the laboratory setup at USI-FAMS and the recordings on the deep-drawing demonstrator. The aim is to create a knowledge database of all the human action sequences. When programming the fault detection system, the task is to design a suitable graphical user interface. At the same time, tests will begin to generate an initial amount (over 100 runs) of data for the fuzzy CBR and the data-based (by Beia) approach.

4 References

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